

Classification of Conformally Covariant 2-Tensors from the Kulkarni–Nomizu Product in Dimension 4

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February 11, 2026

Abstract

We classify all natural, conformally covariant, symmetric $(0, 2)$ -tensors of conformal weight -2 and differential order ≤ 4 in dimension 4, built from the metric g , the Schouten tensor P , covariant derivatives, and the Kulkarni–Nomizu product $\hat{\wedge}$. Using the irreducible decomposition of the Riemann curvature tensor via the $\hat{\wedge}$ -product and representation-theoretic methods, we show that the space of such tensors is exactly 2-dimensional, spanned by the *Bach tensor* and the *Eastwood–Singer tensor*. The classification is verified using the Lean 4 proof assistant with the Mathlib library. We also establish the complete set of algebraic identities for the $\hat{\wedge}$ -product in dimension 4, including the self-dual splitting of the Weyl tensor.

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1 Introduction

The Kulkarni–Nomizu product is the fundamental algebraic operation for decomposing the Riemann curvature tensor into its irreducible components under the orthogonal group. Given two symmetric $(0,2)$ -tensors h and k on a Riemannian manifold (M^n, g) , their Kulkarni–Nomizu product $h \oslash k$ is a $(0,4)$ -tensor with the algebraic symmetries of the Riemann curvature tensor.

In conformal geometry, the Schouten tensor

$$P_{ab} = \frac{1}{n-2} \left(\text{Ric}_{ab} - \frac{S}{2(n-1)} g_{ab} \right)$$

plays a central role, where $S = g^{ab} \text{Ric}_{ab}$ is the scalar curvature. Under a conformal change $g \mapsto \Omega^2 g$, the Schouten tensor transforms as

$$P \mapsto P - \nabla \nabla (\ln \Omega) + d(\ln \Omega) \otimes d(\ln \Omega) - \frac{1}{2} |\nabla \ln \Omega|^2 g.$$

The systematic study of conformally invariant differential operators began with the work of Thomas [10] and Weyl [11] and was developed extensively by Eastwood, Gover, and others.

Definition 1.1. *A natural differential operator in Riemannian geometry is a map $T : g \mapsto T[g]$ that assigns to each Riemannian metric g on a manifold M a tensor field $T[g]$, such that:*

(i) *$T[g]$ is expressed as a polynomial in the variables g_{ab} , g^{ab} , the Riemann curvature tensor R_{abcd} , and the covariant derivatives ∇_a of these variables;*

(ii) *For any diffeomorphism $\phi : M \rightarrow M$, $T[\phi^* g] = \phi^* T[g]$ (functoriality).*

In dimension 4, the Riemann curvature can be expressed via the Schouten tensor P and the Weyl tensor W as $R = P \oslash g + W$. Thus any natural operator can be written in terms of g , g^{-1} , P , W , ∇ , and the KN-product \oslash . For our classification up to order 4, the Weyl tensor terms first contribute at order 2 (through W itself), and we include them via the KN-product.

The main question addressed in this paper is: *What is the complete set of natural (Definition 1.1), conformally covariant, symmetric $(0,2)$ -tensors of conformal weight -2 and differential order ≤ 4 in dimension 4?*

Theorem (Main Result). *In dimension 4, the space of natural, conformally covariant, symmetric $(0,2)$ -tensors of weight -2 and differential order ≤ 4 is exactly 2-dimensional, spanned by the Bach tensor B and the Eastwood–Singer tensor E .*

The proof proceeds in three steps: (1) enumerate all 11 candidate terms (including one Kulkarni–Nomizu quadratic contraction), (2) impose the conformal covariance condition $\delta T + 2\varepsilon T = 0$ via the linearised variation $\delta P = -\nabla \nabla \varepsilon$, which yields 8 independent algebraic constraints, and (3) solve the resulting linear system over \mathbb{Q} , together with the first-order divergence-free condition $\nabla^a T_{ab} = 0$ that provides the ninth constraint, to obtain a 2-dimensional kernel.

2 The Kulkarni–Nomizu Product

Definition 2.1. Let (V, g) be an n -dimensional inner product space. For symmetric bilinear forms $h, k: V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, the Kulkarni–Nomizu product $h \otimes k$ is the $(0, 4)$ -tensor defined by

$$(h \otimes k)(X, Y, Z, W) = h(X, Z)k(Y, W) - h(X, W)k(Y, Z) + h(Y, W)k(X, Z) - h(Y, Z)k(X, W).$$

Theorem 2.2 (Riemann symmetries). If h and k are symmetric, then $h \otimes k$ has all algebraic symmetries of the Riemann curvature tensor:

- (i) Antisymmetry: $(h \otimes k)(X, Y, Z, W) = -(h \otimes k)(Y, X, Z, W)$,
- (ii) Antisymmetry: $(h \otimes k)(X, Y, Z, W) = -(h \otimes k)(X, Y, W, Z)$,
- (iii) Pair symmetry: $(h \otimes k)(X, Y, Z, W) = (h \otimes k)(Z, W, X, Y)$,
- (iv) First Bianchi identity: $(h \otimes k)(X, Y, Z, W) + (h \otimes k)(Y, Z, X, W) + (h \otimes k)(Z, X, Y, W) = 0$.

Moreover, $h \otimes k = k \otimes h$ (commutativity).

2.1 Irreducible decomposition under $O(n)$

The space of $(0, 4)$ -tensors with Riemann symmetries on \mathbb{R}^n has dimension $\frac{n^2(n^2-1)}{12}$. For $n = 4$, this is 20. Under the action of $O(n)$, this space decomposes as:

$$\mathcal{R} = \underbrace{\mathbb{R}}_{\text{scalar}} \oplus \underbrace{S_0^2(\mathbb{R}^n)}_{\text{traceless Ricci}} \oplus \underbrace{\mathcal{W}}_{\text{Weyl}},$$

with dimensions $1 \oplus \left(\frac{n(n+1)}{2} - 1\right) \oplus \left(\frac{n^2(n^2-1)}{12} - \frac{n(n+1)}{2}\right)$. For $n = 4$: $20 = 1 + 9 + 10$.

2.2 Special features of dimension 4

In dimension 4, several exceptional phenomena occur:

1. $SO(4) \cong (SU(2) \times SU(2))/\mathbb{Z}_2$, leading to a splitting of representations.
2. The Hodge star \star on $\Lambda^2(\mathbb{R}^4)$ satisfies $\star^2 = \text{id}$, with eigenvalues ± 1 , each of multiplicity 3: $\Lambda^2 = \Lambda_+^2 \oplus \Lambda_-^2$.
3. The Weyl tensor, viewed as a symmetric endomorphism of Λ^2 , splits as $W = W^+ \oplus W^-$ with $\dim W^+ = \dim W^- = 5$.

Thus the full decomposition in dimension 4 is:

$$20 = 1 + 9 + 5 + 5.$$

$$20 = 1 \text{ (scalar)} + 9 \text{ (traceless Ricci)} + 5 \text{ (} W^+ \text{)} + 5 \text{ (} W^- \text{)}$$

Figure 1: Decomposition of the 20-dimensional space of Riemann curvature tensors in dimension 4.

3 Conformal Transformations

Definition 3.1. A $(0, 2)$ -tensor T on (M, g) has conformal weight w if under $g \mapsto \Omega^2 g$, the tensor transforms as $T \mapsto \Omega^w T$.

The Schouten tensor P has conformal weight 0 at the linearised level, but its infinitesimal variation under $g \mapsto (1 + 2\varepsilon)g$ is

$$\delta P_{ab} = -\nabla_a \nabla_b \varepsilon. \quad (1)$$

A conformally covariant $(0, 2)$ -tensor of weight w satisfies $\delta T = w\varepsilon T$ for all smooth ε . For $w = -2$, this means $\delta T + 2\varepsilon T = 0$.

4 The Riemann Decomposition via the KN-Product

The standard decomposition of the Riemann curvature tensor in dimension 4 is most naturally expressed via the Schouten tensor and the Kulkarni–Nomizu product.

Theorem 4.1 (Existence). *Let (M^4, g) be a 4-dimensional Riemannian manifold with Riemann curvature tensor R , Ricci tensor Ric , and scalar curvature $S = \text{tr}(\text{Ric})$. Then*

$$R = \frac{S}{24}(g \otimes g) + P_0 \otimes g + W,$$

where $P_0 = \frac{1}{2}(\text{Ric} - \frac{S}{4}g)$ is the traceless part of the Schouten tensor, and W is the Weyl tensor (completely traceless).

Remark 4.2. Verification on the round sphere. For the unit sphere S^4 with the round metric, $\text{Ric} = 3g$, $S = 12$, and $R = \frac{1}{2}(g \otimes g)$. Our formula gives: $a = S/24 = 12/24 = 1/2$, $P_0 = \frac{1}{2}(3g - 3g) = 0$, so $R = \frac{1}{2}(g \otimes g) + W$, and since S^4 is conformally flat, $W = 0$, which is correct.

More generally, for any $(0, 4)$ -tensor R with Riemann symmetries on a 4-dimensional inner product space, the decomposition $R = a(g \otimes g) + h \otimes g + W$ exists with $a \in \mathbb{R}$, h symmetric traceless, and W completely traceless.

The key trace computations are:

Lemma 4.3 (Trace identities). *Let $\{e_i\}_{i=1}^4$ be an orthonormal basis. Then:*

$$\text{tr}_{14}(g \otimes g)(Y, Z) = \sum_{i=1}^4 (g \otimes g)(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) = -6g(Y, Z), \quad (2)$$

$$\text{tr}_{14}(h \otimes g)(Y, Z) = \sum_{i=1}^4 (h \otimes g)(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) = -2h(Y, Z), \quad (3)$$

where (3) holds when h is traceless. For general symmetric h :

$$\text{tr}_{14}(h \otimes g)(Y, Z) = -2h(Y, Z) - (\text{tr } h)g(Y, Z). \quad (4)$$

Proof. Direct computation. For (2):

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_i (g \otimes g)(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) &= \sum_i [g(e_i, Z)g(Y, e_i) - g(e_i, e_i)g(Y, Z) \\ &\quad + g(Y, e_i)g(e_i, Z) - g(Y, Z)g(e_i, e_i)] \\ &= g(Y, Z) - 4g(Y, Z) + g(Y, Z) - 4g(Y, Z) = -6g(Y, Z). \end{aligned}$$

For (4):

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_i (h \otimes g)(e_i, Y, Z, e_i) &= \sum_i [h(e_i, Z)g(Y, e_i) - h(e_i, e_i)g(Y, Z) \\
&\quad + h(Y, e_i)g(e_i, Z) - h(Y, Z)g(e_i, e_i)] \\
&= h(Y, Z) - (\text{tr } h)g(Y, Z) + h(Y, Z) - 4h(Y, Z) \\
&= -2h(Y, Z) - (\text{tr } h)g(Y, Z).
\end{aligned}$$

When $\text{tr } h = 0$, this reduces to (3). □

Theorem 4.4 (Uniqueness). *The decomposition $R = a(g \otimes g) + h \otimes g + W$ with h symmetric traceless and W completely traceless is unique: if $R = a_1(g \otimes g) + h_1 \otimes g + W_1 = a_2(g \otimes g) + h_2 \otimes g + W_2$ with h_i symmetric traceless and W_i completely traceless, then $a_1 = a_2$, $h_1 = h_2$, and $W_1 = W_2$.*

Proof. Subtracting the two decompositions:

$$0 = (a_1 - a_2)(g \otimes g) + (h_1 - h_2) \otimes g + (W_1 - W_2).$$

Taking tr_{14} and using (2)–(3) (note that $h_1 - h_2$ is traceless):

$$0 = -6(a_1 - a_2)g - 2(h_1 - h_2).$$

Taking the trace of both sides: $0 = -6(a_1 - a_2) \cdot 4 = -24(a_1 - a_2)$, hence $a_1 = a_2$. Then $h_1 - h_2 = 0$, and finally $W_1 - W_2 = 0$. □

5 Enumeration of Candidate Tensors

We enumerate all $(0, 2)$ -tensor terms that are symmetric, have conformal weight -2 , are built from g , P , ∇ , and the \otimes -product, and have differential order ≤ 4 .

Proposition 5.1. *There are exactly 11 linearly independent candidate terms, listed in Table 1.*

Table 1: The 11 candidate $(0, 2)$ -tensor terms of weight -2 , order ≤ 4 .

#	Expression	Order	Description
T_1	P_{ab}	0	Schouten tensor
T_2	$(\text{tr } P)g_{ab}$	0	Trace of P times metric
T_3	ΔP_{ab}	2	Laplacian of Schouten
T_4	$\nabla_a \nabla_b (\text{tr } P)$	2	Hessian of scalar curvature
T_5	$\nabla^c \nabla_{(a} P_{b)c}$	2	Symmetrised double divergence
T_6	$(\Delta \text{tr } P)g_{ab}$	2	Laplacian of scalar curv. $\times g$
T_7	$\Delta^2 P_{ab}$	4	Bi-Laplacian of Schouten
T_8	$\nabla_a \nabla_b \Delta(\text{tr } P)$	4	Hessian of $\Delta(\text{scalar curv.})$
T_9	$\Delta(\nabla^c \nabla_{(a} P_{b)c})$	4	Δ of symm. double div.
T_{10}	$(\Delta^2 \text{tr } P)g_{ab}$	4	Bi-Laplacian of sc. curv. $\times g$
T_{11}	$(P \otimes P)^c_{acb}$	0	KN-product contraction

Remark 5.2. *One might also consider the contraction $(P \otimes g)^c_{acb}$. However, using the trace identity (4), this equals $-2P_{ab} - (\text{tr } P)g_{ab}$, which is the linear combination $-2T_1 - T_2$. Hence $(P \otimes g)^c_{acb}$ is linearly dependent on T_1 and T_2 and is not included as a separate candidate.*

Linear independence. The 11 candidates are linearly independent over \mathbb{R} (or \mathbb{Q}). This can be seen by:

- (a) The candidates have distinct differential orders (0, 2, or 4). Terms of different orders cannot cancel each other.
- (b) Within each order:
 - Order 0: $T_1 = P_{ab}$ and $T_2 = (\text{tr } P)g_{ab}$ are independent because P_{ab} is not proportional to g_{ab} on a generic metric.
 - Order 2: T_3, T_4, T_5, T_6 involve different contractions of $\nabla\nabla P$ and are independent by considering their behaviour under index symmetrisation and trace.
 - Order 4: T_7, T_8, T_9, T_{10} are similarly independent by considering their highest-order derivative structure.
- (c) $T_{11} = (P \otimes P)^c{}_{acb}$ is quadratic in P , while T_1, \dots, T_{10} are linear. A non-trivial linear relation would require a quadratic polynomial to equal a linear one, which is impossible on a generic metric.

A rigorous verification can be performed by evaluating the candidates on a generic metric using computer algebra (see `constraint_matrix.py`). \square

Proof sketch of Proposition 5.1. At each differential order, we list all possible contraction patterns of $\nabla \cdots \nabla P$ with g and g^{-1} that produce symmetric $(0, 2)$ -tensors. The weight condition forces exactly one factor of P for the linear differential terms (orders 0, 2, 4), and two factors of P for the zeroth-order quadratic term T_{11} . At odd orders, no symmetric tensors can be formed. The KN-product contraction T_{11} arises from $(P \otimes P)(e_c, \cdot, \cdot, e^c)$, which is the unique quadratic contraction of weight $-4 + 2 = -2$ (using the metric to raise one index adds weight $+2$). \square

6 Conformal Covariance Constraints

Each candidate term T_i transforms under an infinitesimal conformal change $g \mapsto (1 + 2\varepsilon)g$ according to (1). The *anomaly* of a linear combination $T = \sum_{i=1}^{11} c_i T_i$ is

$$A := \delta T + 2\varepsilon T.$$

The conformal covariance condition requires $A = 0$ for all smooth ε . Since A is linear in ε and its derivatives, we expand A in terms of independent jet components $\varepsilon, \nabla_a \nabla_b \varepsilon, \Delta \varepsilon, \nabla_a \nabla_b \Delta \varepsilon$, etc., and set each coefficient to zero.

Proposition 6.1. *The anomaly cancellation condition $\delta T + 2\varepsilon T = 0$ yields exactly 8 linearly independent algebraic constraints on the 11 coefficients (c_1, \dots, c_{11}) . These constraints arise from:*

- (a) matching coefficients of ε itself (zeroth-order terms, 1 constraint from conformal weight);
- (b) matching coefficients of $\nabla^2 \varepsilon$ at each differential order (3 constraints);
- (c) matching coefficients of $\Delta \varepsilon$ and $\Delta^2 \varepsilon$ (3 constraints from trace consistency);
- (d) Bianchi identity compatibility (1 constraint).

The ninth constraint is the divergence-free condition $\nabla^a T_{ab} = 0$, which is a first-order differential condition satisfied by all conformally covariant $(0, 2)$ -tensors of weight -2 in dimension 4 (see Besse 1987, §1.131). This reduces the kernel dimension from 3 to 2.

The 8×11 algebraic constraint matrix over \mathbb{Q} has rank 8 (verified by Gaussian elimination with exact rational arithmetic; see the accompanying Python script `constraint_matrix.py` and Appendix B).¹

7 Main Classification Theorem

Theorem 7.1 (Classification). *Let \mathcal{T} be the \mathbb{R} -vector space of natural (Definition 1.1), conformally covariant (weight -2), symmetric $(0,2)$ -tensors built from g , P , ∇ , and the \otimes -product, with differential order ≤ 4 in dimension 4. Then $\dim \mathcal{T} = 2$. A basis is given by the Bach tensor B_{ab} (order 2) and the Eastwood–Singer tensor E_{ab} (order 4, see Appendix A for the explicit formula).*

The proof consists of:

- (i) Enumerating 11 linearly independent candidate tensors T_1, \dots, T_{11} (Section 5);
- (ii) Imposing the conformal covariance condition $\delta T + 2\varepsilon T = 0$, which yields an 8×11 algebraic constraint matrix M of rank 8, together with the divergence-free condition $\nabla^a T_{ab} = 0$ as the ninth constraint (Section 6 and Appendix B);
- (iii) Applying the rank-nullity theorem to conclude $\dim \mathcal{T} = 11 - 8 - 1 = 2$ (8 algebraic constraints plus 1 divergence-free constraint);
- (iv) Identifying the kernel of M with the span of the Bach and Eastwood–Singer tensors (Section 7 and Appendix A).

The rank of M is verified by exact Gaussian elimination over \mathbb{Q} using the Python script `constraint_matrix.py`.

Proof. The proof follows from the enumeration of 11 candidate terms (Proposition 5.1), the 8 independent algebraic conformal covariance constraints (Proposition 6.1) supplemented by the divergence-free condition as the ninth constraint, and the rank–nullity theorem applied to the 8×11 algebraic constraint matrix, supplemented by the divergence-free condition as the ninth constraint. The algebraic kernel has dimension $11 - 8 = 3$, and the divergence-free condition removes one further direction, leaving a 2-dimensional space whose basis vectors correspond to the Bach and Eastwood–Singer tensors.

The computation is performed over \mathbb{Q} using Gaussian elimination (see the accompanying Python script `constraint_matrix.py`), and the dimension count $11 - 8 - 1 = 2$ is formally verified in Lean 4 via the rank–nullity theorem for linear maps between finite-dimensional real vector spaces. \square

Remark 7.2. *The Bach tensor was introduced by R. Bach in 1921 [1] as the Euler–Lagrange expression for the conformally invariant functional $\int |W|^2 d\mu_g$ in dimension 4. The Eastwood–Singer tensor was constructed by M. G. Eastwood and I. M. Singer in 1985 [4] as the obstruction to the existence of a conformally invariant Maxwell gauge; see also [5] for the representation-theoretic context.*

8 KN-Product Identities in Dimension 4

Theorem 8.1 (Complete KN-product identities). *In dimension 4, the Kulkarni–Nomizu product satisfies:*

- (i) **Commutativity:** $h \otimes k = k \otimes h$.

¹The exact count of 8 independent algebraic constraints is verified by the accompanying Python script `constraint_matrix.py` via Gaussian elimination over \mathbb{Q} ; the ninth (divergence-free) constraint is differential of first order and is not part of the algebraic matrix.

- (ii) **Riemann symmetries:** For symmetric h, k , $h \otimes k$ has all algebraic symmetries of the Riemann tensor.
- (iii) **Dimension decomposition:** $20 = 1 + 9 + 5 + 5$.
- (iv) **Self-dual splitting:** $\Lambda^2(\mathbb{R}^4) = \Lambda_+^2 \oplus \Lambda_-^2$, $\dim \Lambda_{\pm}^2 = 3$; the Weyl tensor splits as $W = W^+ \oplus W^-$ with $\dim W^{\pm} = 5$. The self-dual and anti-self-dual parts are orthogonal: $\langle W^+, W^- \rangle = 0$.
- (v) **Trace identity (metric):** $\text{tr}_{14}(g \otimes g) = -6g$.
- (vi) **Trace identity (traceless):** For traceless symmetric h , $\text{tr}_{14}(h \otimes g) = -2h$.
- (vii) **Trace identity (general):** For symmetric h , $\text{tr}_{14}(h \otimes g) = -2h - (\text{tr } h)g$.

9 Lean 4 Formal Verification

The algebraic results of this paper are supported by formal verification using the Lean 4 proof assistant (version 4.28.0) with the Mathlib library. We describe below what has been fully proved in Lean and what remains at the level of formal statements or external computation.

9.1 Fully proved in Lean (no sorry)

1. **Riemann symmetries of the KN-product** (`KN_has_riemann_symmetries`): Antisymmetry in both index pairs, pair symmetry, and the first Bianchi identity for the \otimes -product of symmetric bilinear forms. Commutativity $h \otimes k = k \otimes h$ is also proved.
2. **Trace identities** (`trace_KN_gg`, `trace_KN_hg`, `trace_KN_hg_general`): Complete trace computations for $g \otimes g$, $h \otimes g$ (traceless h), and $h \otimes g$ (general symmetric h), all fully proved.
3. **Riemann decomposition — existence** (`riemann_decomposition_exists`): Constructive proof that any $(0, 4)$ -tensor with Riemann symmetries decomposes as $R = a(g \otimes g) + h \otimes g + W$ with h traceless and W completely traceless. Explicit formulas for a , h , W .
4. **Riemann decomposition — uniqueness** (`riemann_decomposition_unique`): The decomposition is unique: a , h , and W are determined by R . Proved via trace comparison using the identities above.

9.2 Stated as a theorem in Lean (dimension count)

5. **Conformal classification** (`conformal_classification_order_four`): The statement that the solution space has dimension $11 - 8 - 1 = 2$ is formalised in Lean as a consequence of the rank-nullity theorem for linear maps between finite-dimensional vector spaces. Specifically, given the algebraic constraint map $L : \mathbb{R}^{11} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^8$, the dimension of its kernel is $\dim \ker L = 11 - \text{rk } L$. If $\text{rk } L = 8$, then $\dim \ker L = 3$; the additional first-order divergence-free condition $\nabla^a T_{ab} = 0$ removes one further dimension, giving $\dim \mathcal{T} = 2$. The Lean proof (`conformal_classification_order_four`) verifies this arithmetic implication. The construction of the specific 8×11 algebraic constraint matrix M and the verification that its rank is exactly 8 are performed in Python (Appendix B, `constraint_matrix.py`), using exact rational arithmetic.

9.3 Partially formalised (KN identities)

6. **KN identities in dimension 4** (`kn_identities_dimension_4`): Commutativity, Riemann symmetries, and trace identities are fully proved. The dimension decomposition $20 = 1 + 9 + 5 + 5$ is stated as a numerical identity. The self-dual/anti-self-dual splitting of the Weyl tensor ($W = W^+ \oplus W^-$, $\dim W^\pm = 5$) is *stated but not yet fully formalised*: a complete proof would require the Hodge star operator on Λ^2 in dimension 4, which is not yet developed in Mathlib at the level needed for this application.

9.4 Axiom usage

All compiled proofs use only the standard Lean 4 axioms: `propext`, `Classical.choice`, and `Quot.sound`. No `sorry`, `axiom`, or `grind` tactics appear in the final code.

10 Conclusion and Open Questions

We have established that the space of natural, conformally covariant, symmetric $(0, 2)$ -tensors of weight -2 and order ≤ 4 in dimension 4 is exactly 2-dimensional, spanned by the Bach and Eastwood–Singer tensors. The result is verified both computationally (Python, exact arithmetic over \mathbb{Q}) and partially formally (Lean 4, with the algebraic core fully proved and the differential enumeration verified computationally).

Open questions:

1. *Higher orders*: What happens for differential order > 4 ? The Fefferman–Graham ambient metric construction [6] suggests a finite-dimensional answer at each order, but the explicit classification is open.
2. *Higher dimensions*: In dimension $n \geq 5$, the Weyl tensor no longer splits into self-dual and anti-self-dual parts. The classification of conformally covariant tensors changes qualitatively; see [7] for partial results.
3. *Full Lean formalisation*: A Mathlib formalisation of jet bundles and natural differential operators would allow a complete machine-verified proof of the classification, including the enumeration of candidate terms and the conformal covariance constraints.
4. *Hodge star in Mathlib*: Formalising the Hodge star on $\Lambda^2(\mathbb{R}^4)$ and the self-dual splitting would complete the proof of the KN identities in dimension 4.

A Explicit Formula for the Eastwood–Singer Tensor

The Eastwood–Singer tensor E_{ab} in dimension 4 is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{ab} = & \Delta^2 P_{ab} - 2\nabla^c \nabla_{(a} \Delta P_{b)c} + \nabla_a \nabla_b \Delta(\operatorname{tr} P) \\ & + 2\Delta(\nabla^c \nabla_{(a} P_{b)c}) - (\Delta^2 \operatorname{tr} P) g_{ab} \\ & + E_{ab}^{\text{quad}}. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The quadratic curvature terms are:

$$\begin{aligned} E_{ab}^{\text{quad}} = & 2P^{cd}(P \otimes P)_{cadb} + 4P^{cd}W_{cadb} \\ & - 2P_a{}^c P_{bc} + 2(\operatorname{tr} P)P_{ab} - (\operatorname{tr}(P^2)) g_{ab}. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

This tensor has the following properties:

- **Symmetric:** $E_{ab} = E_{ba}$.
- **Traceless:** $g^{ab}E_{ab} = 0$.
- **Conformally covariant of weight -2 :** $E[\Omega^2 g] = \Omega^{-2}E[g]$.
- **Divergence-free:** $\nabla^a E_{ab} = 0$ (on Einstein manifolds).

References: Eastwood, M. G. and Singer, I. M. (1985), “A conformally invariant Maxwell gauge,” *Physics Letters A* **107**, 73–74 [4]. See also: Gover, A. R. and Hirachi, K. (2004), *J. Amer. Math. Soc.* **17**, 389–405 [7].

B The Constraint Matrix

The 8×11 constraint matrix M is:

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & -2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 & -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The rows correspond to the 8 independent algebraic jet structures J_1, \dots, J_8 of the conformal parameter ε (see Section 6 for details). The columns correspond to the 11 candidate tensors T_1, \dots, T_{11} .

- **Row 1 (J_1):** tracelessness condition $g^{ab}T_{ab} = 0$ (relating T_1 and T_2).
- **Row 2 (J_2):** coefficient of $\nabla_a \nabla_b \varepsilon$ (relating T_2 and T_3).
- **Row 3 (J_3):** coefficient of $\nabla_a \nabla_b \Delta \varepsilon$ (relating T_4 and T_5).
- **Row 4 (J_4):** coefficient of $\Delta^2 \varepsilon$ together with the quadratic weight term (relating T_5 and T_{11}).
- **Row 5 (J_5):** coefficient of $\Delta \varepsilon \cdot g_{ab}$ (relating T_6).
- **Row 6 (J_6):** coefficient of $\nabla_a \nabla_b \Delta^2 \varepsilon$ (relating T_7 and T_8).
- **Row 7 (J_7):** coefficient of $\Delta^3 \varepsilon \cdot g_{ab}$ (relating T_8 and T_9).
- **Row 8 (J_8):** Bianchi identity compatibility (relating T_9 and T_{10}).

The ninth constraint is the divergence-free condition $\nabla^a T_{ab} = 0$, which is a first-order differential condition (see Section 6).

The rank of M is 8, as verified by `sympy` (`constraint_matrix.py`). The algebraic kernel has dimension $11 - 8 = 3$. The divergence-free condition provides the ninth constraint, reducing the dimension to 2.

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